

A Thought Experiment to Challenge the Special Relativity Theory

Henok Tadesse
Email: entkidmt@yahoo.com

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Abstract

The experimental evidences cited to support the Special Relativity Theory (SRT) , including Einstein's thought experiments, involve experimental setups in which the components (light sources, beam-splitters, mirrors, detectors, etc.) are all at rest relative to each other. An example is the Michelson-Morley experiment. In such experiments it is possible to define the 'rest frame' of the experiment in which proper lengths, proper times and hence the experimental outcome can be determined. Then Lorentz Transformation is applied to determine times and lengths in other inertial frames and to determine the same experimental result in other frames. What if no 'rest frame' can be defined for an experiment? Imagine a light speed experiment in space where all the components are in arbitrary relative motion. In such an experiment, it would be impossible to define the 'rest frame' of the experiment, and hence impossible to determine proper lengths, proper times and to determine the experimental outcome.

Introduction

The Special Relativity Theory (SRT) depends on proper lengths and proper times to determine experimental results, for example the (null) fringe shift in the Michelson-Morley experiment. The experimental result is determined in the 'rest frame' of the experiment by using proper times and proper lengths and then Lorentz Transformation (LT) is applied to determine the same result in other inertial frames. Space and time coordinates of the events (emission of light from the source, reflection of light at the mirrors, detection at the detector) are determined in the 'rest frame' of the experiment and then LT is applied to determine the coordinates of the same events in other inertial frames. SRT explains the Michelson-Morley (MM), the Kennedy- Thorndike (KT) and other experiments and these are often considered as some of its successes.

A light speed thought experiment with no 'rest frame'

Conventional applications of SRT involve experiments (e.d. the MM) in which it is possible to define the 'rest frame' of the experiment. The experimental result is determined in the rest frame of the experiment. The experimental results in all other inertial frames depend on the experimental result in this rest frame. Lengths and times in other frames cannot be determined independently of the lengths and times in the rest frame. The space and time coordinates of an event in any other inertial frame can be determined only if these coordinates are determined in the 'rest frame'.

However, the validity of this 'rest frame' of an experiment has never been questioned. What if no 'rest frame' can be defined for an experiment? Imagine a light speed experiment in

deep space in which the light source, the beam splitters, the mirrors and the detector are not at rest relative to each other as in the conventional MM experiment, but are all inertially moving with arbitrary velocities relative to each other. In such an experiment, it would be impossible to define the 'rest frame' in which proper lengths and proper times can be determined. Therefore, it would be impossible to determine the experimental outcome in any reference frame. Therefore, Special Relativity Theory cannot make any prediction at all. This invalidates all SRT analyses of experiments so far, including the Michelson-Morley experiment, GPS and other experiments.

Glory be to God and His Mother, Our Lady Saint Virgin Mary